

Articles

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Financing India's Renewable Energy Targets: Modes and Challenges

Abstract

The Renewable Energy Sector of India is considered to be the world's second most attractive Renewable Energy market.¹ In terms of the total, installed wind power capacity, India ranks fourth worldwide. In the previous year itself, (i.e. January-November 2017) India added 11.788 GW of the total power generation capacity from renewable sources.² With the Government's increased support, along with enhanced, developed and improved economics, the Renewable Energy Sector is becoming more and more attractive to investors. The energy demand of India is expected to reach 15,820 TWh by 2040³ and as India is gearing up to become self-sufficient and meet this requirement on its own, Renewable and Clean energy is expected to take on an important role. It is expected that by 2040, 49% of the total electricity obtained is to be generated through renewable energy⁴.

With the commitment of the Government of India to increase use of clean energy sources, the Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE) has set a target to set up renewable energy capacities to the extent of 175 GW by 2022⁵ (which includes 100 GW from Solar, 60 GW from Wind, 10 GW from Biopower and 5 GW from Small Hydro power units⁶), as was announced in 2015. To fund this ambitious plan, India would need at least US\$ 125 billion.⁷ The 'renewable energy industry' financing is considered difficult due to its characteristics of high initial investment, investment risk and dicey long-term investment returns. Keeping this as a backdrop, this article aims at discussing the various Financing modes currently in use and the various financing challenges to be faced in meeting India's Renewable Energy Targets in the coming years.

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Prelude

The last few years have experienced growing concerns over climate change, which has led to governments and industries across economies seeking to supply energy and meeting their countries' energy requirements by creating new measures to aid in minimizing environmental impacts such as gas emissions and the like. Countries are facing issues such as limited stock of Fossil Fuel, increased carbon emissions and Global Warming and have thus started investing in green energy, which now seems to be the best alternative and the only possible future. A major policy strategy across many economies is the employment of Renewable Energy Sources. The access to clean energy and meeting sustainable holistic development goals are reasons that have led to the transformation of many developing countries to more sustainable economies. The increase in population growth, higher living standards and energy demands influence the development of any country. According to estimations, the global population is going to be 2.3 billion more by 2050 while energy demand is to increase by 21% by 2030.⁸ This will have major implications on the infrastructure of the energy sector and how the energy needs will be met in future. All this would then naturally be directed at efficiency, effectiveness and economy. Any decision made in the sector would have effects throughout the economy considering its direct connection to sustainability of a country's economy. Access and availability of timely finance remains a challenge in many developing countries.

1.1 Renewable Energy: Global Scenario

In 2016, worldwide, renewable energy (excluding large hydro plants) accounted for 55.3% of the new electricity generating capacity. This was the second successive year it had exceeded 50%.⁹ In order of Net GW installed in 2015, Solar Power added significantly more GW followed by Wind, Coal, Gas, Large Hydro, Nuclear and Biomass. In 2016, Renewable energy (excluding large hydro) produced an estimated 11.3% of the world's electricity, an increase from 10.3% in 2015 and 6.9% in 2011.¹⁰

New Investments in Renewable Power Globally and Fuels Today in Developed, Emerging and Developing Countries, 2006-2016

Renewable energy investment in developed countries, went down by 14% to USD 125 billion in 2016.¹¹ The investment in Japan and the United States fell, while Europe saw a marginal increase in the same. While Renewable energy investment fell 30%, to USD 116.6 billion, among developing and emerging countries¹². In terms of investment in Renewables in 2016, capacity went down by 23% in terms of dollars (\$) (world total), though of course the year was a

strong year for investment in energy smart technologies.¹³ Asset finance for smart meters and energy storage, plus equity, raised for specialist companies in energy efficiency, storage and electric vehicles, went up by 29% to \$41.6 billion.¹⁴

The main reasons for the decline in global investment in renewable energy during 2016 could be enumerated as:

1. the slowdown in investments in Japan, China and some other emerging countries and
2. the significant cost reductions in solar PV and onshore and offshore wind power, which led to the improvement of cost-competitiveness of those technologies.¹⁵

This resulted in investors being able to acquire more Renewable energy capacity for lesser price.

Note: Figure does not include investment in hydropower projects larger than 50 MW. Investment totals have been rounded to nearest billion.

Source: BNEF

Source: REN21, "Renewables 2017 Global Status Report" (Paris: REN21 Secretariat).

Fig 1: Global New Investment in Renewable Power and Fuels: Developed, Emerging and Developing Countries, 2006-2016.

1.2 India’s Renewable Energy Sector

1.2.1 Sector Overview

Source: IBEF¹⁶

Fig. 2: Renewable Energy Sector

According to IBEF Sector Report¹⁷, the CAGR in installed capacity over the period FY07 to forecasted FY18 was 2.32 % for Hydro power and 20.12 % for other renewable energy sources. The Government of India projects 17.04% CAGR increase in other RES installed capacity to 275 GW by 2027. The total renewable power generation installed capacity in India stood at 103.92 GW as on July 2017 accounting for 31.2 % of the total installed capacity, with hydro power forming the largest source of energy accounting for over 43% of the total renewable power generation installed capacity.

Source: IBEF¹⁸

Fig. 3: Renewable Energy Sector Trends

1.2.2 Targets for Renewable Power Installed Capacity and/or Generation

The target for renewable power installed capacity has been set at 175GW to be achieved by 2022.

India	Capacity (not specified)	175 GW by 2022
	Bio-power	10 GW by 2022
	Hydropower (small-scale)*	5 GW by 2022
	Solar PV	20 million solar lighting systems added 2010-2022
	Solar PV and CSP	100 GW by 2022
	Wind power	60 GW by 2022
Andhra Pradesh	Solar PV	5,000 MW added between 2015 and 2020
Jharkhand	Solar PV	2,650 MW installed by 2019-2020

Source: REN21 Renewables 2017 Global Status Report (Paris: REN21 Secretariat).

Fig. 4: Targets for renewable power installed capacity and/or generation

As per a Climate Policy Initiative report, the renewable energy sector in India will require 189 Billion USD in additional investment in order to meet this target which includes 57 billion USD in equity, and \$132 billion in debt (the report has estimated this using capital expenditure forecasting for renewable energy projects between 2016 and 2022).¹⁹ According to the report, the potential for investment in the renewable energy sector is 411 billion USD up to 2022 which is more than double of the investment required. The investment potential for equity and for debt is \$220 billion and \$191 billion respectively which indicates that there is a huge investment potential is available for financing India's Renewable Energy Targets by the year 2022.²⁰

2. Financing India's Renewable Energy Targets: Financing Modes and Challenges

2.1 New Investment in Renewable Power and Fuels Trend from 2006 to 2016

Source: REN21, *Renewables 2017 Global Status Report* (Paris: REN21 Secretariat).²¹

Fig. 4: New Investment in Renewable Power and Fuels

2.2 Financing India's Renewable Energy Targets: Financing Modes

2.2.1 Equity

Equity is one of the traditional sources of financing renewable energy is Equity. The sources of equity capital for renewable energy projects have seen a significant change: from majority of the projects being funded by Private equities, Corporates, Venture Capitals and the alternate investment markets, as was seen between 2009-2013, (which itself indicated the relatively high risk involved in the business) to funding through pension funds, sovereign funds, large Indian and Global utilities and infrastructure investment trusts²², that have and will be triggered by the scale of renewable energy businesses and policies governing the sector and financing of the same.

2.2.2 Debt

As was observed in Equity, debt funding for renewable energy projects also saw significant changes in terms of the source of the financing. Initially, renewable energy projects were funded by banks and NBFCs. Of late, while there has been an expansion in bank debt financing, in terms of flexibility of leverage, the infrastructure debt funds are predominant in refinancing the operating renewable energy projects.²³ This has led to improvements of the returns from projects and thus reducing the debt load on the balance sheets of banks and NBFCs, further enabling enhanced lending. The most noteworthy development in debt financing has been the ability of renewable energy projects to access the same through debt capital markets. Over the last few years, there have been significant issuances of bonds from both domestic and international investors.

The two most innovative debt capital market instruments have been 'Green Bonds' and 'Masala Bonds' that have led to further improvement in the pricing and returns of the projects²⁴. Masala bonds refer to Bonds that are issued outside India but denominated in Indian Rupees, rather than in their local currency.²⁵ In Masala Bonds, the investors bear the risk, as opposed to dollar bonds where the borrower takes the currency risk.²⁶ Green Bonds are financial instruments where the proceeds are set aside for investing exclusively in renewable energy, energy efficiency and other climate smart projects in developing countries.²⁷ Green Bonds aid in raising capital and investment for existing and new projects with environmental benefits.²⁸ Since the time SEBI issued its Green Bond Regulations in May 2017, the cumulative Green Bond issuance in India has more than doubled to \$6.5 billion.²⁹

The other sources of financing renewable energy projects include foreign financial agencies like the US export-import bank (EXIM) and the Asian Development Bank (ADB), funds from them are generally routed through banks and NBFCs.³⁰

Current incentives impacting financing of renewable energy include:³¹

- (a) The National Clean Energy Fund (NCEF), created to support entrepreneurial ventures and research in the field of clean energy technologies, and soft loans from Indian Renewable Energy Development Agency (IREDA)
- (b) Tax free bond issuance – The Government has permitted a few entities, IREDA among them, to issue tax free bonds to the public in terms of Section 10(15)(iv)(h) of the Income Tax Act and the CBDT Notification, with interest rate lower than comparable bonds and having long tenures of 10, 15, and 20 years, which provides the entities with cheaper sources of funding and in which the benefits can be passed on to the borrower.³²

2.2.3 Mergers and Acquisitions (M&As)

India is emerging as one of the most attractive countries for renewable energy investment. Experts in the industry feel that renewable energy is expected to see momentous activity in terms of capital-raising and M&As.³³ According to an article,³⁴ the sector has seen a number of M&A's drivers in the form of few projects set up by corporates whose core business was not power development and their objective to invest was solely to utilize the additional cash available to generate "annuity revenues" and with the industry scaling up and returns getting constrained there, many of them wanted to exit their investment; secondly, of a number of PE funded renewable energy IPPs that were established between

2009 and 2013, while the large players were able to raise fresh equity, the sub 300 MW platforms, not having being able to, preferred consolidation; and thirdly with India emerging to be one of the largest market in renewable energy, a lot of global players have shown interest in the same and have taken M&A as a route to enter the Indian market.

2.3 Financing India's Renewable Energy Targets: Challenges

2.3.1 The Investment Gap: Potential and Expected³⁵

Source: Sen et al, "Reaching India's Renewable Energy Targets: The Role of Institutional Investors", December 2016, <https://climatepolicyinitiative.org/publication/reaching-indias-renewable-energy-targets-role-institutional-investors/>

A Climate Policy Initiative report, “Reaching India’s Renewable Energy Targets: The Role of Institutional Investors”,³⁷ spoke of the gap between the potential investment versus the expected investment in the Renewable Energy Sector in India. It went on to say that the highest potential to bridge this gap was through foreign as well as domestic investors. Even though the equity capital from FIIs is slightly more expensive than from the other sources, they have the potential to finance 100% of the equity financing gap. And while the cost of capital from DIIs is highly cost effective, they have the potential of financing 54% of the debt financing gap. An increase in the understanding of the sector may make it an attractive investment for the otherwise risk averse institutional investors.³⁷

Banks and NBFCs will also have an important contribution towards investment in this priority sector, as the need of the hour is to invest more in clean and green technology for achieving effectiveness, efficiency and economy.

2.3.2 Cost of Financing

One of the main issues in Financing Renewable Energy is the extreme cost of financing. Unlike Fossil Based Energy Technologies, Renewable Energy Technologies have high Capital costs though the operating costs are low and are usually spread over a period of 25-30 years. Currently the cost of finance ranges between 12-14%.³⁸ Since cost of finance is a substantial component of the Power tariff, a reduction in the same could bring down the Power Tariffs hence enabling an increase in demand for Renewable Energy. The cost of finance is influenced by multiple factors.

2.3.3 The Risk Perception

Given that the risk perception of the project, reason and identity of the borrower for/of finance is dominant in any form of financing, and specifically in the financing of renewable energy projects, and especially since the lenders differ in their understanding and ease with the same, the associated risk mitigations measures could help in reducing the perception of risk associated with financing the projects.³⁹ The cost of the debt and the return expectations of investors are dependent on a number of parameters that include project related factors such as operating period, length of construction period, stage of construction, the presence of power purchase agreements, financial health of distribution utilities, and market and economic factors such as the state of economy, risk free rate, inflation expectations, risk weights, type of financing and the like. Financing the sector looks attractive due to factors such as absence of fuel supply issues, shorter gestation periods, and lower operational costs in

comparison to conventional projects. But, there are also a few key risks associated with financing renewable energy projects, predominant among them being the regulatory risk and the continuity of incentives. While there are “mechanisms such as preferential/ feed in tariffs, renewable purchase obligation (RPO), renewable energy certificates (REC), income tax holiday – 80IA benefits, accelerated depreciation (AD), generation based incentive (GBI), duty and tax exemption / concessional duty for imports, etc.” that make this sector investment extremely attractive, the challenges of uncertainties in continuity and non-uniformities show a lot of room for improvement.⁴⁰

2.2.4 The Culmination: Financing Challenges in Meeting the Renewable Energy Targets

1. Regulatory/ Policy Risk: Policy changes and implementations contribute significantly to investment trends. The following are the possible challenges:⁴¹

- (a) Regulatory risk and continuity of incentives
- (b) Non-uniformity in policy guidelines at central and state levels
- (c) Uncertainty and divergence in feed-in tariffs approved by SERCs
- (d) Lack of long-term Renewable purchase obligation trajectory and its compliance

2. Economic Risks for Lenders: The key risk here is how much of the returns and by when can the returns be expected considering the timeline of the projects, and considering that the investments are huge; how much risk is the lender/ investor willing to take. Renewable energy projects need huge capital investments, and usually the cost of such investments is higher than the cost of financing of fossil technologies. The concerns and challenges for the investors/ lenders of Finance could be:

- (a) Payback Period of the Project (PBP)
- (b) Opportunity cost
- (c) Return on Investment (ROI)

3. Operational Efficiency: The Operational risks and the project related risks could throw quite a few challenges such as:⁴²

- (a) Financial losses of distribution utilities and non-payment
- (b) Inadequate evacuation and transmission infrastructure
- (c) Capacity Utilization Factor (CUF) degradation

4. Inconsistent Power Generation in few Renewable energy technologies in comparison to conventional energy generation directly questions efficiency on

investment. The output of Wind and Solar Photovoltaic is not constant, and especially in the case of wind the output can be very uncertain.⁴³

5. Technological Risk: Continuous change in technology with rising technology costs lead to the technological risk in the sector.

6. Public and Societal Concerns: With the need for clean energy and depleting natural resources as the drivers to increased need for investment in renewable and clean energy, the following could hence be the major public and societal concerns:

- (a) Land acquisitions
- (b) Forest Clearance

3. Epilogue

Renewable energy is the now the key factor to the future of energy, efficiency, ecological balance and economic security. The various benefits of renewable energy include zero fuel, reduced imports and reduced pollution. It has a huge potential to overcoming the future energy crisis and its impacts on the economy and ecology. In this context, India has already embarked on an ambitious path of increasing its renewable energy share in the country's energy mix, having set a target to achieve 175 GW of installed renewable energy capacity by the year 2022. The finance landscape for the renewable energy sector is on the brink of dramatic change. Mechanisms for lowering cost of investments in the sector will help renewable energy supersede other energy technologies. Few recommendations were made to lowering financing cost for the renewable sector as was mentioned in the paper "Enabling Low-cost Financing for Renewable Energy in India", based on their research were Synthesized products, Tax free Bonds, Capital gains tax Bonds, Inflation Free Bonds, Tradable tax credits, Government/Intermediaries Guarantees and Reduction of Sovereign Guarantee Fee.⁴⁴

The initial efforts to install stations and plants capable of generating renewable energy were driven by environmental considerations and climatic changes. With countries striving to fulfill these pledges under the Paris Agreement, they are increasing focus as well as resources on augmenting renewable energy capacity within the country and setting more ambitious targets for the same. The need for scaling up renewable energy sources, be it Solar, Wind, Hydro, Bio energy and others to meet the international climate goals needs huge investments. The challenges in financing in the renewable energy sector can be addressed through various risk-mitigating strategies and techniques, instruments and structured finance mechanisms. The India advantage is that

there is a high renewable energy potential and with new initiatives from the Central and State Governments, India can capture the benefits by increasing and raising the required investments.

Notes

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